

Impact of rough building material surfaces on reflection coefficients from 5 GHz to 260 GHz

Jean-Marc Conrat[§], Jean-Christophe Cousin^{*}, Xavier Begaud^{*}

[§] Wireless Engineering and Propagation, Orange Labs, Belfort, France, jeanmarc.conrat@orange.com

^{*} LTCI, Telecom Paris, Institut Polytechnique de Paris, Palaiseau, France

Abstract—When an electromagnetic wave is reflected by a smooth and planar surface, its amplitude is decreased by the Fresnel reflection coefficients depending on the material permittivity, incidence angle and polarization. Recent work showed that the permittivity does not depend on the frequency from 2 to 260 GHz implying that the reflection gain is constant from 2 to 260 GHz for a given incidence angle and polarization. But Fresnel coefficients are only valid for materials with a smooth surface which is not always the case for building materials. Materials such as concrete or patterned glass may be rough or have a relief surface. This paper analyzes the reflection gain deviation from the Fresnel coefficients when material surfaces are not smooth and proposed a simplified model based on the Rayleigh-Rice or Beckmann-Kirchhoff theoretical approaches. The investigated frequencies ranged from 5 to 260 GHz.

Index Terms—reflection loss, scattering, sub-THz, 6G

I. INTRODUCTION

Ray tracing are popular deterministic propagation channel models to evaluate the performance of wireless radio interfaces or to predict the coverage area [1][2]. They use a geographical database or digital map to compute all possible rays i.e., direct, reflected, transmitted, diffracted, scattered paths, between two or more points such as transmitter, receiver, Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface (RIS), relay, etc. The ray amplitude and geometrical features are given by physical laws according to the interaction type between the electromagnetic (EM) wave and the environment. This paper focuses on reflected paths. The reflection coefficient indicates the reflection gain experienced by a path when reflected by a material surface. The reflection coefficients are theoretically given by the Fresnel equations for a planar smooth surface bounding a uniform material. They depend on the material relative permittivity ϵ_r , the incidence angle and the EM wave polarization. Many deterministic simulations use the relative permittivity proposed by the ITU-R P2040 recommendation [3] where the permittivity is considered as a constant regardless of the frequency. It implies that the reflection loss does not depend on the frequency. The ITU-R P2040 model is mainly defined up to 100 GHz but recent work [4][5] shows that the model could be extended up to 300 GHz with flat surface materials such as glass or plexiglass. Nevertheless, some differences were observed for materials with rough or relief surfaces at frequency above 50 GHz. The goal of this paper is to assess the reflection coefficient deviation from a model considering a constant permittivity when material

surfaces are not smooth. The investigated frequencies ranged from 5 to 260 GHz.

II. SPECULAR REFLECTION VS DIFFUSE SCATTERING

When the EM wave propagating through the air encounters an object, a fraction of the wave is reflected at the interface level air/object. The reflection transfer function $H_r(f)$ is defined as the ratio between the reflected and incidence wave. The reflection is specular when the incident wave impinges on a smooth and planar surface and is reflected in a single direction defined by the Snell's laws. The paper addresses mainly the normal incidence illustrated by Fig. 1. The reflection coefficient at the air/material interface r_{Mut}^{Air} is equal to $\frac{1-\sqrt{\epsilon_{mut}}}{1+\sqrt{\epsilon_{mut}}}$ according the Fresnel equations, ϵ_{mut} being the relative permittivity of the Material Under Test (MUT) considered as a low-loss dielectric. The relative permittivity does not change significantly with the frequency and can be modeled as a constant. Hence, $H_r(f)$ on a smooth surface is constant and equal to r_{Mut}^{Air} . The specular reflection gain (SRG) expressed in dB is equal to $10 * \log_{10}(|r_{Mut}^{Air}|^2)$.

Fig. 1. Specular reflection and scattering illustration at normal incidence

If the surface is rough, then scattering occurs and the incident wave is scattered into many directions in addition to the specular direction as illustrated in Fig. 1. The wave power reflected in the specular direction is diminished as a portion of the incident wave is reradiated in various scattered directions. Consequently, Fresnel equations may overestimate $H_r(f)$ in the specular direction when the surface is rough.

A simple approach for accounting the scattering in the specular reflected direction is to consider a correction factor ρ_s that depends on the roughness and the frequency. $H_r(f)$ on rough surfaces is equal to $\rho_s r_{Mut}^{Air}$. The theoretical Rayleigh-

Rice (RR) scattering factor ρ_s^{RR} defined as $\rho_s^{RR} = e^{-g/2}$ is often cited in literature as a potential correction factor [6][7][8]. g is the Rayleigh roughness factor and is equal to $\left(\frac{4\pi\sigma_h\cos(\theta)}{\lambda}\right)^2$, λ being the wavelength, θ the incidence angle and σ_h the surface height variation. $g=0$, $g \ll 1$, $g > 1$ and $g \gg 1$ indicates respectively a smooth surface, a slightly rough surface, a moderately rough surface and a very rough surface. ρ_s^{RR} was calculated according to some assumptions such as small values of g and a gaussian surface height distribution. It may not be applicable to all building materials. For instance, [9] shows a good agreement between measurements and a simulation implementing ρ_s^{RR} for $g=0.2$ whereas the simulation overestimates the reflection loss by 20 dB for g values higher than 5. Another theoretical approach is given by the Beckmann-Kirchhoff (BK) scattering model that is similar to the RR model for $g \ll 1$ but is more accurate for $g \gg 1$ [10][11]. The scattering factor ρ_s^{BK} can be approximated by $\frac{\sqrt{\pi}l_c}{\sqrt{A}\sqrt{g}}$ for $g \gg 1$, with A the scattering surface area and l_c the height correlation length. l_c is defined as the distance at which the autocorrelation of a surface height linear profile drops to e^{-1} . A high correlation length means smooth transitions between the highest and lowest surface points. ρ_s^{BK} is valid for a surface area that shall be small enough to respect the far-field condition. Therefore, $H_r(f)$ on large rough surfaces such as walls cannot be computed by multiplying r_{Mut}^{Air} by ρ_s^{BK} . The BK model implementation in a ray tracing requires a wall segmentation into small tiles. It increases the ray tracing complexity and may not be essential to compute the power in the specular direction. This paper proposes a simple and empirical model based on the RR and BK models to compute ρ_s in the specular direction for small and large values of g .

III. MEASUREMENT SETUP AND CHARACTERIZED MATERIALS

The measurement equipment is based on a vector network analyser (VNA) and frequency extenders. The measurement is divided into three sub-bands defined by the frequency limits of the VNA, extenders, or antennas (5-40 GHz, 110-170 GHz, 170-260 GHz). The antenna is a dual-ridge ultra-wideband antenna for frequencies below 40 GHz and a standard horn pyramidal antennas for frequencies above 50 GHz.

Fig. 2. Measurement setup

Fig. 2 illustrates the mechanical part that allows a free space measurement for reflection coefficients. The Tx/Rx measurement antenna can move on a vertical plane and therefore can scan the material by performing a $m \times n$ measurement matrix. A 11×11 measurement matrix with points separated by 1 cm was performed. The role of the measurement matrix is to check the impact of the reflection point location on the reflection coefficient. MUT was placed at normal incidence facing the Tx/Rx antenna in the material holder middle. The Tx-Rx distance for frequencies below 40 GHz and for frequencies above 110 GHz is equal to 60 cm and 120 cm respectively. The MUT illuminated area corresponding to the antenna half power angular beamwidth is equal to $40 \times 40 \text{ cm}^2$ at frequencies above 110 GHz and ranges between 30×30 and $50 \times 50 \text{ cm}^2$ at frequencies below 40 GHz.

Mortars with different roughness degrees and patterned glass shown in Fig. 3 were measured to assess the impact of rough surfaces on reflection coefficients.

Fig. 3. Characterized Materials

The MUT surfaces were scanned with a laser system. Surface height linear profile examples are given in Fig. 4 to illustrate the surface roughness. The average correlation length l_c is equal to 0.6 mm, 2.5 mm, 8 mm, 4 mm, 1.2 mm for Mortar A, Mortar B, Mortor C, Mortar D, Patterned Glass respectively. The surface roughness is also statistically characterized by the surface height Probability Density Function (PDF) and by the surface height standard deviation σ^h given in Fig. 5.

Fig. 4. Surface height linear profiles. The profile is shifted by -1 mm, 1 mm, 2mm, 3mm for Patterned Glass, Mortar C, Mortar B, Mortar A respectively

Fig. 5. Surface height PDF

IV. DATA PROCESSING

The raw material measurements are denoted by $S_{11}^{Meas}(f, m, n)$ and corresponds to the S11 parameter collected by the VNA. $S_{11}^{Met}(f)$ is a reference measurement by replacing the MUT with a metallic plate considered as a perfect reflector. $H_r^{Mut}(f, m, n)$ represents the MUT intrinsic reflection frequency response and is computed according to (1)

$$H_r^{Mut}(f, m, n) = \frac{TG[S_{11}^{Meas}(f, m, n)]}{TG[S_{11}^{Met}(f, m, n)]} \quad (1)$$

$TG[.]$ is the time gating operator. It is a temporal filter applied on the inverse fast Fourier transform (IFFT) of S parameters that rejects all undesirable components such as wall reflections or material edge diffractions. The time gating operator is also configured to keep only the reflection on the illuminated material side facing the transmitter and reject the reflection on the opposite side as illustrated by Fig. 6

Fig. 6. Illustration of the time gating operator on $S_{11}^{Meas}(f, m, n)$

$ppH^{Mut}(f, m, n)$ is defined as the power profile of $H^{Mut}(f, m, n)$ and is equal to $10\text{Log}_{10}(|H^{Mut}(f, m, n)|^2)$ when expressed in dB. $ppH_{Mean}^{Mut}(f)$ is defined as the average power profiles of $H^{Mut}(f, m, n)$ and is equal to $10\text{Log}_{10}\left(\frac{1}{mn}\sum_{m,n}|H^{Mut}(f, m, n)|^2\right)$ when expressed in dB.

$\sigma^{Mut}(f)$ is defined as the standard deviation of $ppH^{Mut}(f, m, n)$ at frequency f calculated on the $m \times n$ measurement point matrix. $\sigma^{Mut}(f)$ characterizes the reflection gain variation due to the different reflection point locations as illustrated by Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Average and standard deviation of $ppH^{Mut}(f, m, n)$ for Mortar B

The frequency fading observed on $ppH^{Mut}(f, m, n)$ is due to the interferences between the specular component and the scattered components diffused from surface points close to the theoretical specular reflection point as illustrated by Fig. 8. Consequently, $ppH^{Mut}(f, m, n)$ is geometrically dependent on the MUT illuminated area and results presented in this paper may not be valid for other Tx/Rx distances or antenna angular apertures. It implies to check if the measurement setup can collect all scattered paths.

Fig. 8. Scattering angle definition

α is the scattering angle defined as the angle between the scattered path direction and the MUT normal direction. $h^{Mut}(t, m, n)$ is the reflected impulse response defined as the inverse Fourier Transform of $H^{Mut}(f, m, n)$. $pph_{Mean}^{Mut}(t)$ is the average power profile of $h^{Mut}(t, m, n)$. Fig. 9 displays $pph_{Mean}^{Mut}(t)$ as function of α for frequencies between 170 and 260 GHz. This frequency band was selected as scattering is assumed to have the greatest impact at higher frequencies. The MUT impulse response is compared with the response by a metallic plate. When the $pph_{Mean}^{Mut}(t)$ shape for the different materials is similar to the $pph_{Mean}^{Metal}(t)$ shape, the scattered waves are mainly received in the specular direction with α roughly lower than 5° . When $pph_{Mean}^{Mut}(t)$ is larger than

$pph_{Mean}^{Metal}(t)$, the scattered waves are received with a scattering angle higher than 5° and the received power may be underestimated due to the limited antenna angular aperture or the limited MUT dimension. Fig. 9 indicates that the specular direction is the predominant direction even for very rough materials such as Mortar C or Mortar D. Consequently, observations or conclusions drawn in the following sections can be extended to other Tx-Rx distances or antenna pattern.

Fig. 9. $pph_{Mean}^{Mut}(t)$ as function of α . The metal response is shifted by 10 dB

V. DATA ANALYSIS AND MODEL

First, the impact of rough surfaces is analyzed by visual inspection of $pph_{mean}^{Mut}(f)$ and $\sigma^{MUT}(f)$ plotted in Fig. 10 and Fig. 11 respectively. SRG is computed with permittivity values in line with [3][4] for concrete ($\epsilon_{Mortar}=5.3$) and glass ($\epsilon_{Glass}=6.3$). When the frequency increases and/or when the surface roughness increases, $pph_{mean}^{Mut}(f)$ decreases as expected by the scattering models described in section II. For frequencies below 40 GHz, $pph_{mean}^{Mut}(f)$ is close to SRG for mortars A, B, C indicating that scattering is negligible. But at frequencies above 100 GHz, $pph_{mean}^{Mut}(f)$ is reduced compared to SRG by around 5 dB for mortar C and 10 dB for mortar D. The measured reflection gain strongly depends on the reflection point location. For instance, $\sigma^{MUT}(f)$ for mortar A is always lower than 1 dB but reaches 5 dB for mortars C and D above 100 GHz. Scattering may erase the specular reflected path at some reflection point locations as the reflection gain may be lower than -20 dB for frequencies above 100 GHz. Conclusions drawn to rough surfaces such as mortar surfaces can be extended to any relief surface such as patterned glass.

Fig. 10. $pph_{mean}^{MUT}(f)$ for the different materials

Fig. 11. $\sigma^{MUT}(f)$ for the different materials

Second, the measured scattering factor ρ_s^{Meas} is computed for the different materials. ρ_s^{Meas} expressed in dB is equal to $pph_{mean}^{MUT}(f) - SRG$. ρ_s^{Meas} is plotted as function of g in Fig. 12 and Fig. 13 with different g -scales. It is compared with ρ_s^{RR} and with measured or simulated values extracted from literature. [13] reports simulations at 28 GHz with an incidence angle of 30° on plasterboard with different surface roughness. [14] reports reflection measurement with an incidence angle of 45° at 100, 200, 300 and 400 GHz for a rough surface with $\sigma_h=0.38$ mm. The comparison between the scattering factor and the Rayleigh roughness factor leads to the following conclusions:

- ρ_s^{Meas} is highly correlated with parameter g but some variations can be observed between materials for $g>2$. It might be due to different l_c values between materials. ρ_s^{Meas} tends to decrease when l_c tends to decrease as suggested by the BK model but there is no clear mathematical relation between ρ_s^{Meas} and l_c . Consequently, it makes sense to propose a simple model that depends only on g .
- ρ_s^{RR} is in agreement with the measurement for small values of g and may be used with $g < 1$. The RR model overestimates the scattering loss for $g>1$ and should be replaced by a model proportional to $1/\sqrt{g}$ as suggested by the BK model.

- There is a lack of measurement for $g > 4$ and data extracted from literature gives different results. It is not straightforward to propose a simple model for large values of g but measurement results on the roughest mortar at frequencies above 110 GHz indicates that ρ_s^{Meas} is constant for $g > 30$. This can be explained intuitively by the fact that the mortar surface is viewed as multiple large facets generating multiple specular reflections. Increasing g by increasing the frequency does not change the reflected transfer function.

Based on the previous observations, the following modified scattering model is proposed. The calibration coefficients were selected in order to minimize the discontinuities at $g=1$ and $g=10$.

Fig. 12. Comparison between measured or modelled scattering factors

Fig. 13. Comparison between measured or modelled scattering factors

VI. CONCLUSION

Measurements have been done to characterize reflection coefficients on rough or relief surfaces for typical building materials between 5 to 260 GHz. Rough surfaces behave like smooth surfaces at frequency below 40 GHz except for very rough mortar. The reflection coefficient may be decreased

compared to the theoretical Fresnel coefficient by 5 dB to 15 dB in average at frequencies above 100 GHz for slightly and very rough surfaces respectively.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. W. Mbugua, Y. Chen, L. Raschkowski, L. Thiele, S. Jaeckel and W. Fan, "Review on Ray Tracing Channel Simulation Accuracy in Sub-6 GHz Outdoor Deployment Scenarios," in *IEEE Open Journal of Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 2, pp. 22-37, 2021
- [2] D. He, B. Ai, K. Guan, L. Wang, Z. Zhong and T. Kürner, "The Design and Applications of High-Performance Ray-Tracing Simulation Platform for 5G and Beyond Wireless Communications: A Tutorial," in *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 21, n°1, pp. 10-27, 2019
- [3] ITU-R, "Effects of building materials and structures on radiowave propagation above about 100 MHz," Recommendation ITU-R P.2040-3, Aug., 2023.
- [4] Jean-Marc Conrat, Mohamed Aliouane, Jean-Christophe Cousin, Xavier Begaud, "Material Permittivity and Conductivity Estimation From 2 to 260 GHz and Extension of the ITU-R P.2040 Model at Frequency Above 100 GHz", Personal, Indoor, Mobile Conference (PIMRC) 2024, Valencia, Spain, Sept. 2024
- [5] Jean-Marc Conrat, Mohamed Aliouane, Jean-Christophe Cousin, Xavier Begaud, "Building Material Permittivity and Conductivity Estimation from 2 to 260 GHz", European Microwave Conference (EuMC) 2024, Paris, France Sept. 2024
- [6] S. Ju et al., "Scattering Mechanisms and Modeling for Terahertz Wireless Communications," *IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC)*, Shanghai, China, 2019, pp. 1-7
- [7] R. Piesiewicz, C. Jansen, D. Mittleman, T. Kleine-Ostmann, M. Koch and T. Kurner, "Scattering Analysis for the Modeling of THz Communication Systems," in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 55, no. 11, pp. 3002-3009, Nov. 2007
- [8] F. Sheikh, Q.H. Abbasi and T. Kaiser, "On channels with Composite Rough Surfaces at Terahertz Frequencies," *European Conference on Antenna and Propagation (EuCap) 2019*,
- [9] F. Sheikh, Y. Zantah, I.B. Mabrouk, M. Alissa, J. Barowski, I. Rolfes, T. Kaiser, "Scattering and Roughness Analysis of Indoor Materials at Frequencies from 750 GHz to 1.1 THz" in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 69, no. 11, pp. 7820-7829
- [10] F. Sheikh, Y. Gao and T. Kaiser, "A Study of Diffuse Scattering in Massive MIMO Channels at Terahertz Frequencies," in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 68, no. 2, pp. 997-1008, Feb. 2020
- [11] C. Jansen et al., "Diffuse Scattering from Rough Surfaces in THz Communication Channels," in *IEEE Transactions on Terahertz Science and Technology*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 462-472, Nov. 2011
- [12] P. Xie, K. Guan, D. He, H. Yi, J. Dou and Z. Zhong, "Terahertz wave propagation characteristics on rough surfaces based on full-wave simulations", *Radio Science*, 57, 2022
- [13] S. Bakirtzis, T. Hashimoto and C. D. Sarris, "FDTD-Based Diffuse Scattering and Transmission Models for Ray Tracing of Millimeter-Wave Communication Systems," in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 69, no. 6, pp. 3389-3398, June 2021
- [14] J. Ma, R. Shrestha, W. Zhang, L. Moeller and D. M. Mittleman, "Terahertz Wireless Links Using Diffuse Scattering From Rough Surfaces," in *IEEE Transactions on Terahertz Science and Technology*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 463-470, Sept. 2019.